

VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL IMPACT OF GENDER ASPECT IN ENGLISH ADVERTISEMENTS

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Abstract: *This article describes and analyzes about some features of verbal and non-verbal impact of gender aspect in English advertisement.*

Keywords: *verbal impact, non-verbal impact, gender, gender aspects, English advertisements.*

The modern English word gender comes from the Middle English gender, gender, a loanword from Anglo-Norman and Middle French genre. The concept of gender, in the modern sense, is a recent invention in human history. The ancient world had no basis of understanding gender as it has been understood in the humanities and social sciences for the past few decades. The cultural content of advertising, its language and its connection with gender issues are deeply rooted in our society. Language and gender are significant issues that remain widely controversial in the domain of advertising. Advertising is a common phenomenon nowadays and people are exposed to the advertising process wherever they are and it has gained the attention and interest of a large number of individuals in different societies around the globe. Advertising is referred to as a form of discourse in the sense that it has influenced not only the structure of language and the modality of lifestyle, but also the content of routine daily acts of communicative exchanges. The messages of advertising have permeated the entire cultural landscape. Printed advertisements fill the pages of newspapers and magazines. Commercials interrupt TV and radio programs constantly. Advertising is a prevalent phenomenon nowadays that has gained the attention and interest of a large number of individuals in different societies around the globe. People are exposed to the advertising process wherever they are. Advertising is not only an 'ideal tool' for reaching people economically, but it is a device of attaining and maintaining contact with persons socially, culturally, politically and even psychologically. Therefore, advertising is neither an innocent way of selling products nor the primary

factor which changes society's attitudes and behavior so as to fulfill its ends and economic purposes.

In an advertisement equal attention should be addressed to both verbal and nonverbal communication components. The role of nonverbal communication is repeating, conflicting, replacing and highlighting or mitigating the verbal component. Nonverbal communication includes physical characteristics of a person: communication, movements and pose, and the communication environment. Although both verbal and nonverbal communication components are often used and stressed separately, their synergy should be recognized and appropriately used.

The research results can be used as a guideline in creating new ideas for commercials as nonverbal advertising components can enhance the desired product perception. In order to create a communication message a company can use several nonverbal elements, like for example music, gestures, symbols etc. To enhance its desired perception among customers all these nonverbal elements together with verbal components should be carefully unified to provide a communication message. Moreover, if the experience of using a product is positively related with its perception established through advertising, high brand awareness is present. As a consequence, customers buy other products of the same brand or recommend the brand to friends, hence, customer loyalty is experienced.

Furthermore, depending on the product category, non-verbal communication contributes to a greater or lesser, but always positive extent in evaluating characteristics of a person that uses the advertised product. Therefore, non-verbal communication can be used to augment the desired brand perception. Careful building and conveying the desired brand perception through non-verbal messages will enhance its desired brand image. Similarly, First and Garzinch concluded that the desired brand image should be created by choosing ad appeal that best suits target customers' driving needs. Therefore, a desired brand image can be enhanced if a company carefully combines non-verbal communication with adequately chosen ad appeal that suites its target market. The research results could serve advertising agencies in finding optimal ratio among different personal characteristics that are planned to be used for creating the brand image.

Several limitations have been noticed. As two out of three brands that are used in the research are present on the market, the brand recognition could have influenced respondents' reactions. Hence, the brand recognition as well as attitudes toward brands used in the research could

have influenced the perception of certain product's characteristics. For further research it is suggested to compare brands related to specialty or luxury products as well as to explore reactions based on commercials for brands with which respondents are familiar and others that they are completely unfamiliar with and not present on the market. Moreover, it would be interesting to conduct a research on a bigger differentiated sample so that the difference in gender/age could be explored. Generally, we can conclude that verbal and non-verbal impact of gender aspect in English advertisements occurred in both printed and video formats are one of the biggest units of English world and still we have some problems to be solved.

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